

Development of chimeric antigen receptor macrophages (CAR-M) and modeling of macrophage intratumoral infiltration in breast cancer model

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes how data will be generated, documented, stored, protected, and, where possible, shared during the project “Development of chimeric antigen receptor macrophages (CAR-M) and modeling of macrophage intratumoral infiltration in breast cancer model,” which develops and functionally evaluates HER2-targeted CAR macrophages (including SIRP α knockout variants) and investigates macrophage migration in breast cancer models using in vitro 2D/3D assays and in vivo imaging approaches. The purpose of the DMP is to ensure that all resulting experimental, imaging, and analytical outputs are managed consistently across the project lifecycle, remain secure and traceable, and are prepared for dissemination in line with FAIR and open science requirements, including preparing the plan in a suitable DMP platform (e.g., ARGOS using the Latvian Council of Science blueprint) and publishing the DMP (and, when appropriate, underlying datasets/metadata) via repositories such as Zenodo with clearly defined access conditions.

Funder

Atvērto Atveseļošanas fonds (Recovery and Resilience Facility) RRF grant No.56/BMC/ZG (RRF

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project

No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001)

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Researchers

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Organizations

Latvian Biomedical Research and Study Centre

1. Main Info

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Atveseļošanas fonds (Recovery and Resilience Facility) RRF grant No.56/BMC/ZG (RRF project No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/001)

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3. License

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Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

DMP

Targeting cancer cells with genetically modified T cells expressing chimeric antigen receptors (CARs) represents

an innovative and relatively efficient immunotherapy approach, especially for the treatment of blood cancers.

However, the broader application of CAR-T cells for solid tumors faces limitations, including inefficient tumor

infiltration, the induction of cytokine release syndrome in patients, and the risk of neurotoxicity. In this project,

we propose a novel strategy where CAR technology is harnessed to modify macrophages, enabling CAR

dependent phagocytosis of cancer cells. Macrophages, as highly potent effector cells, possess the unique ability to

infiltrate solid tumors, engulf cancer cells, and stimulate T-cell activation. We propose to develop a new type of

CAR macrophages with enhanced phagocytic abilities and establish optimal conditions for their intratumoral

migration. The project will facilitate a better understanding of the functions of genetically modified macrophages

and establish a powerful platform for therapeutic interventions.

Keywords: cancer immunotherapy, chimeric antigen receptor, macrophages, viral vectors

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of data collection and generation in this project is to design, validate, and functionally evaluate HER2-targeted chimeric antigen receptor macrophages (CAR-M), including SIRP α knockout variants, and to model macrophage intratumoral infiltration in breast cancer systems. The generated data will directly support the project objectives by (i) confirming genetic modification and phenotypic characterization of engineered macrophages, (ii) assessing cytotoxicity, phagocytic activity, cytokine secretion, and migration in 2D and 3D in vitro models, and (iii) evaluating macrophage trafficking and therapeutic performance in in vivo breast cancer models using imaging approaches. The data will originate primarily from laboratory experiments conducted within the project (molecular cloning, cell culture, gene editing, flow cytometry, microscopy, functional assays, and in vivo imaging), and secondarily from processed analytical outputs derived from these primary datasets.

Primary data:

Experimental laboratory data (molecular biology, cell biology, gene editing validation)

Flow cytometry data

Microscopy and imaging data (2D, 3D, in vivo imaging)

Functional assay data (migration, cytotoxicity, phagocytosis, cytokine quantification)

Secondary data:

Processed and normalized quantitative datasets

Statistical analysis outputs

Annotated image analysis results

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- TIFF
- PNG
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

TB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The project primarily generates new experimental datasets. However, publicly available genomic or methodological reference data may be consulted for comparative or validation purposes in accordance with licensing and ethical requirements.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The datasets will be useful to researchers in cancer immunotherapy, macrophage biology, gene editing, and tumor microenvironment research. They may support further development of CAR-based cellular therapies, computational modeling of immune cell infiltration, translational oncology studies, and meta-analyses in immuno-oncology. Processed datasets and metadata may also be valuable for method development, reproducibility assessment, and comparative preclinical research.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

At this stage, the project does not plan to prepare standalone, repository-level metadata records. Data will be documented internally through laboratory notebooks, standard operating procedures, and accompanying methodological descriptions in scientific publications. Essential contextual information required for interpretation (experimental design, materials, methods, and analysis procedures) will be included within publications and internal records rather than as separate structured metadata files.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

MeSH (Medical Subject Headings); Gene Ontology (GO)

<https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

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2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

An embargo period of up to 12 months after publication of main results may be applied to allow protection of intellectual property and completion of primary publications.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard scientific software tools

Title: FlowJo

<https://www.flowjo.com/>

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

MeSH (Medical Subject Headings); Gene Ontology (GO); Cell Ontology (CL); NCBI Gene

<https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Academic Free License 3.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Anna Zajakina (0000-0002-4753-1103)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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